

Civic and political education for elections

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In February 2025, Ecuadorians will vote in a first round of elections. The candidates will be known by October of this year. There will be expressions of interest from political parties and those who claim to answer to the people to run. As in previous elections, media, sports and other figures with little history of public service are likely to be seen.

In this context, there is a clear need for political and civic education so that through consistent spaces for dialogue, consensus and working agendas for the communities can be found. And from these dynamics, a deliberative public opinion can be built. It is forgotten that democracy is more than going to the polls, responding to polls, or consuming the spectacles of aspirants on television or social networks.

Democracy is participation, freedom of expression, assuming the role of citizens through rights and duties for a well-being that is measured in health, education, critical awareness, environmental care, as well as economic growth. In other words, democracy is valued in terms of qualitative and quantitative progress and personal fulfilment within a social framework.

It is not true to think that a candidate, ruler, or leader alone can generate positive changes for his or her constituents; teams, collectives, and groups are needed to join forces and bring diversity to identify common goals.

Another common mistake is homogeneity. Proposing a standard plan for the period of government, ignoring diversities, denying the integration of minority criteria.

Thus, Ecuadorians return to the polls with minimal political training, "objectified", seen as a number, not as people with opinions. Much remains to be done for genuine elections to take place as a result of processes of maturity and intervention.